

ATILIM UNIVERSITY
GRADUATE SCHOOL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES
DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION
BUSINESS MANAGEMENT MASTERS'S PROGRAMME

**THE EFFECT OF PERCEIVED RISKS ON ONLINE SHOPPING
INTENTION: A CASE OF ANKARA**

Master's Thesis

Alaa AL HLAICHI

Thesis Advisor

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Kemal Gürkan KÜÇÜKERGIN

Ankara-2023

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ACCEPTANCE AND APPROVAL

This is to certify that this thesis titled “The Effect Of Perceived Risks On Online Shopping Intention: A Case of Ankara” and prepared by Alaa AL HLAICHI meets with the committee’s approval unanimously/by a majority vote as Master’s Thesis in the field of Business Administration following the successful defense conducted on 4/7/2023.

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ETHICAL STATEMENT

I accept and acknowledge that I have prepared this thesis study, prepared in line with the Thesis Writing Guidelines of Atılım University Graduate School of Social Sciences;

- within the framework of academic and ethical rules;
- presented the information, documents, evaluations, and results in a way that meets the rules of scientific ethics and morality,
- I have referenced each work from which I have benefited while preparing my thesis, and that
- I hereby present a unique study.

I hereby also understand that I shall accept any loss of rights against my behalf in cases otherwise.

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ÖZ

AL HLAICHI, Alaa. Algılanan Risklerin Online Alışveriş Niyeti Üzerindeki Etkisi: Ankara Örneği, Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Ankara, 2023.

Bu araştırma, Türk tüketicilerinin çevrimiçi satın alma niyetleri üzerinde finansal risk, kalite riski ve teslimat riskinin etkisini araştırmaktadır. Çalışmada, katılımcıların kendi yanıtlarını sağladıkları bir anket ve kolayda örnekleme yöntemini kullanarak 300 Türk tüketiciden ampirik veri toplanmıştır. Bu araştırmada finansal riskin, kalite riskinin ve teslimat riskinin çevrimiçi satın alma niyeti üzerinde bir etkisinin olduğu öne sürülmektedir. Bu risk unsurlarının satın alma eğilimi üzerinden olumsuz bir etkisinin olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Sonuçlar, çevrimiçi alışverişle ilgili algılanan riskin değerlendirilmesi ve ele alınması için önemli bir çerçeve sunmakta ve potansiyel olarak Türk tüketicilerin katılımının artmasına ve e-ticaret alanındaki algısal noksanlıkların azalmasına katkı sağlamaktadır.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Algılanan risk, çevrimiçi alışveriş, alışveriş niyeti, Türk tüketicisi, E-ticaret.

ABSTRACT

AL HLAICHI, Alaa. The Effect Of Perceived Risks On Online Shopping Intention: A Case of Ankara, Master's Thesis, Ankara, 2023.

This research investigates the effect of financial risk, quality risk, and delivery risk on the online purchasing intention of Turkish consumers. Using a self-administered survey and convenience sampling, empirical data was collected from 300 Turkish online customers in this study. The research proposes that financial, quality, and delivery risks have a significant effect on online shopping intention. It is discovered that those risks have a negative effect on shoppers' intentions. The results provide a significant framework for assessing and handling the perceived risk associated with online shopping, potentially resulting in heightened participation by Turkish consumers and a decrease in their perceptual shortcomings in the realm of e-commerce.

Keywords: Perceived risk, shopping online, shopping intention, Turkish consumers, E-commerce.

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INTRODUCTION

The concept of engaging in commercial transactions via the internet can be attributed to the initial stages of the 1980s, during which Michael Aldrich devised a mechanism that facilitated communication between purchasers, vendors, providers, intermediaries, and disseminators (Aldrich, 2011). These various classifications of market participants had access to a platform that allowed them to interact with one another and share information concerning the various requirements of their market sector. Aldrich (2011) integrated a communication system with two-way capabilities commonly referred to as "videotex." Different market participants were able to communicate with one another and make their intentions known through the platform. The recipient would then respond appropriately by making arrangements for the delivery of the products for which an order had been placed. Initially, the only method of communication between the two sides was through texting; however, as technology improved, telephone lines were eventually added to the system. This website was known as Mintel, and it enabled customers to carry out a variety of transactions online. The aforementioned transactions encompassed a range of activities, such as engaging in e-commerce for diverse goods and services, booking travel arrangements, monitoring stock market fluctuations via the internet, and conducting searches for telephone directories. In 1984, Tesco, a prominent global retailer, achieved a significant milestone by executing the inaugural internet-based transaction in recorded history. Nissan, an automobile company, was able to successfully complete the first online credit check using the platform in 1985. This accomplishment was made possible by the platform (James Taylor, 2022).

Experience with the internet is another factor that influences online shopping habits; heavy internet users tend to make more purchases online compared to lighter internet users (Loketkrawee & Bhatiasevi, 2018).

Traders had the opportunity to sell their wares in a number of different geographical areas thanks to this platform. The developers made it possible to personalize the website so that it would better meet the unique requirements of the market in a specific area. Customers have access to a wide variety of payment options, including debit and credit cards, and the business is still operational to this day, though somewhat on a much more modest scale. A watershed moment in the history of the

United States was the introduction of Peapod.com in 1989. Peapod.com was the first online marketplace that was dedicated entirely to the business of selling grocery items (James Taylor, 2022).

The emergence of the World Wide Web during the initial years of the 1990s signified the commencement of amplified progressions in the realm of e-commerce. This was due to the fact that the Internet made it simpler for programmers to create additional platforms that assisted in the growth of online commerce (Kulviwat et al., 2006). The introduction of eBay and Amazon, two of the most well-known and successful online shopping platforms ever, in 1995 marked a turning point for the sector. Upon deciding to include a variety of products on their platform, the eBay founders promptly initiated outreach to traders engaged in various types of products, inviting them to test their platform. Meanwhile, Amazon was originally established to serve as a venue for the purchase and sale of books. Nevertheless, the platform's unprecedented growth and success made it almost certain that it would eventually become a trading platform that included everything. The late 1990s saw the introduction of a number of different online payment systems, with PayPal emerging as the most successful of these. Customers' payments were guaranteed to be secure, which made online shopping a more appealing option, which led to a meteoric rise in the popularity of online shopping around the world (James Taylor, 2022).

The online world constitutes a communal, cooperative, and autonomous framework that can be harnessed by a vast number of individuals across the globe. The proliferation of technological advancements related to the Internet has made it possible to make online purchases that are more convenient than those made using more conventional methods. A guarantee of safe financial dealings is extremely important; however, any advances in technological capability must take this into consideration. In spite of the fact that e-commerce is well positioned for significant growth, it is essential to keep an eye on the risk attitudes of consumers in order to encourage additional shoppers to engage in online shopping (Goi, 2016). Consequently, attitude and perceived risk should be considered while examining consumer online purchase intention.

As a result, more transactions will occur, which will substantially impact the expansion of e-commerce. The marketing literature acknowledges that consumer attitudes strongly influence their propensity to place an order or to revert

back to the one they've already placed. Whether the perceived risk is real or not, it will influence a customer's buying choices. To screen their level of effect on shoppers' online behaviors and purchasing attitudes and eliminate discord after a purchase has been made, the research should continuously assess the customer's attitude toward the risk related to online shopping (Hassan et al., 2006). Accordingly, it is essential to study consumer risk attitudes to manage and minimize them clearly, thereby promoting online shopping.

To increase efficiency, innovative technology development is required for online retailers to expand their market share. When used correctly, web software enables online merchants to circumvent size and consumer engagement limits and interact more successfully with large companies. The internet makes it possible for a wider variety of people to start their own businesses, as well as providing an easy method to run a company without being constrained by regular business hours. This expands the pool of people who can participate in the marketplace. Because of this, digital businesses have a greater opportunity to utilize the services of other businesses located all over the world as a key tool. The fact that it tends to increase earnings makes online shopping an attractive option for businesses. If a successful promotional campaign is launched on the internet, promising customers will be informed about it around the world. Furthermore, alongside the exchange of commodities and provisions, customers and companies frequently form business partnerships through the use of online stores (Alkhamery et al., 2021).

In addition, online retailers advertise their wares on the internet, which encourages more customers to do their shopping online. Customers are able to create a shopping screen, search for goods, make a price comparison, purchase, and add items to the basket on websites that are attractively designed. Once the customer has paid for the goods, the goods are delivered to the location that the customer specifies. Retailers who operate online advertise and sell their products. Trust has traditionally been a significant obstacle in the context of online shopping, despite the fact that this industry is experiencing rapid growth. As the number of instances of online fraud and concerns regarding customers' privacy and safety have increased, digital stores have a responsibility to research methods that will help them earn the dependability and devotion of their customers (Habib & Hamadneh, 2021).

It is generally accepted that consumer perceptions of risk have a direct impact on their propensity to make and complete a purchase online. Even if the risk isn't actual, consumers will react negatively to any perceived threat. In order to prevent discord following the completion of purchases, the level of consumer concern must be regularly assessed about the security of their online transactions (Hassan et al., 2006). Consequently, it is crucial to persistently examine consumer risk perceptions, especially after the pandemic, which has changed people's perceptions and attitudes toward many factors, in order to actively manage them to lessen these fears and encourage more people to shop online.

Despite the fact that there are currently a number of studies (Masoud, 2013; Özsürunc, 2017; Wai et al., 2019; Busha'eer et al., 2021) have examined the relationship between perceived risks and shopping intention, this research has been conducted in Türkiye using different aspects and types of risks. It is necessary to track online shoppers' behaviors for an accurate measure to help businesses overcome the risks.

The importance of this study derives from the significance of the perceived risks of electronic purchasing as determinants and influences that discourage consumers' desire to purchase from websites. The importance of this study stems from the following considerations:

- Contribution to the scientific literature on consumer online behavior.
- Faster economic growth and greater consumer satisfaction can be attributed to the widespread availability of digital resources.
- Make a coherent application for the concerns that should be taken into account when making an online purchase.

Thus, the research will examine the impact of perceived risks, specifically in the areas of finance, quality, and delivery, on the online shopping intentions of consumers in Türkiye.

CHAPTER 1: LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 E-commerce

International online trade has been a growing sector in recent years. The growth of international online commerce is causing traditional export trade structures to transform, and an increasing number of businesses involved in international trade are finding new commercial opportunities through ongoing online transactions (Acilar, 2016).

The COVID-19 pandemic has hastened the transition toward online platforms that is occurring in many different industries, including business, education, and industry in general. In tandem with this development, several e-commerce websites have emerged to facilitate online transactions (Munkova et al., 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic has impacted the growth of e-commerce platforms, with notable global shifts observed in various customer attitudes. The offline to online migration of consumer behavior is an example of evolutionary change, in which applications for e-commerce need more accessible designs, greater sustainability, and business intelligence-using software applications. In the course of our research, a few studies focused on the analysis of web accessibility on e-commerce websites as well as the methods and tools that are utilized in automatic inspection (Paștiu et al., 2020; Pollák et al., 2021; Villa & Monzón, 2021). Paz et al., (2021) present their argument in favor of the accessibility that should be designed into software products, including online retail outlets. They suggest that some nations have laws and policies in place that ensure accessibility to websites by taking into account individuals' varying levels of skill and capability.

In previous studies, cross-border online commerce was analyzed primarily from the point of view of geographical distance between markets and consumer welfare. For instance, as far back, Cairncross (1997) started looking into whether or not "death of distance" could be said to apply to online trade. Cowgill & Dorobantu (2013) examined the impact that international e-commerce has on domestic trade by utilizing both data pertaining to trade within a country's borders and digital information across international borders obtained from Google AdWords. They discovered that the expansion of international online business had the effect of cutting trade costs related to geographical distance by 60%. Likewise, Gomez-Herrera et al., (2014) using data

from countries that are part of the European Union (EU), determined that cross-border e-commerce between businesses and consumers (B2C) has been found to have decreased trade costs associated with geographical distance by 30%. According to the findings of these studies, engaging in business across international borders through the use of the internet reduces the amount of time and effort required to engage in trade. In the meantime, several investigations, e.g., Gomez-Herrera et al., (2014) revealed that the costs of doing business associated with overcoming language difficulties increased. This was due to the fact that the infrastructure for cross-border e-commerce is essentially the same as that for offline transactions.

1.1.1 E-business

The term "e-business" refers to a collection of business practices and software applications that enable organizations to leverage internet-based information and communication technologies for both internal and external commercial transactions (Chao, 2016). E-business is defined as a strategy for enhancing organizational competitiveness through the optimization of management practices via the integration of information technology and the Internet. The proposed approach is informed by a comprehensive review of existing literature and culminates in a refined definition (Pilinkiene et al., 2013 p.77). In the body of prior research, e-business capability has received very little attention. The aggregate potential of an entity's information technology (IT) infrastructure encompasses its physical components, digital applications, communal utilities, administrative protocols, and the technical and managerial proficiencies of its staff (Z. Zhu et al., 2015). The ability of an organization to integrate its other resources through the application and allocation of its IT resources is what is meant by the term "IT abilities." The following are the different types of information technology resources: IT intangibles, IT human resources, and IT facilities all come under this category (Cheng et al., 2008 p.1045). The capabilities of information technology can be broken down into three categories: the capabilities of internal communication, the capacities of business procedure modification, and the abilities of tactical change (Zeng & Zheng, 2008). The term "IT capabilities" refers to the amalgamation of skills required to effectively allocate and oversee IT resources, as well as to interact with other resources within an organization in order to achieve shared IT efficiency and corporate goals. This definition includes both the capability of IT infrastructure as well as the skills possessed by IT human resources (Torkzadeh

& Doll, 1999). E-business capability term pertains to the establishment of a business, the transfer and implementation of technological assets for online businesses, the enhancement and maintenance of different core operates that exhibit proficiency and competence, and the cultivation of the potential to sustain ongoing competitive advantages (Schubert & Hausler, 2001). E-business capability refers to an organization's ability to mobilize, deploy, and integrate information resources in conjunction with other enterprise resources and abilities in order to accomplish a particular objective. The capacity for conducting e-business encompasses various aspects (Troshani & Rao, 2007). Drawing upon prior research, it is possible to formulate a theoretical framework for an e-business capability. To clarify, it is possible to transform an information technology capability into a distinct type of capability that is grounded in an electronic business viewpoint, thereby achieving an electronic business capability.

1.1.2 E-commerce and international trade

The implementation of e-commerce is expected to eliminate the adverse effects on both the demand and supply aspects. B2C e-commerce provides consumers with the opportunity to procure products online, thereby obviating the need to physically visit traditional retail outlets (Hayakawa et al., 2023). According to the research conducted by Watanabe & Omori, (2020), there has been a surge in online consumption of goods and services, while offline consumption has witnessed a decline amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. The provision of online sales channels and direct-to-consumer delivery options serves as a means of mitigating potential declines in earnings for producers and retailers (Hayakawa et al., 2023).

Within the realm of global commerce, the utilization of online search functions as a facilitator in pairing vendors with purchasers (Ma & Fang, 2021). Our contention is that the utilization of online search has the potential to not only mitigate unfamiliarity among traders but also diminish trade risks by augmenting trusted transactions. Undoubtedly, conducting online searches can aid in overcoming unfamiliarity. The utilization of robust search engines such as Google has facilitated the process of connecting sellers and buyers at a reduced cost (Goldfarb & Tucker, 2019). This is due to the fact that sellers can conveniently access information regarding foreign markets and promote their merchandise, while buyers can

effortlessly obtain information about product offerings and seller prices (Bakos, 1997). Hence, it is more expedient for traders to engage in transactions with unfamiliar individuals. Conversely, the utilization of online search can serve to mitigate trade risks to some extent. The proliferation of online connections has enabled firms to enhance their ability to make effective initial selections of foreign partners prior to engaging in deal-making activities (Rauch & Trindade, 2003).

An investigation done by Alaveras and Martens (2015) using data sourced from the European Union, the physical distance separating two countries continues to exert a noteworthy impact on the purchasing behavior of consumers who engage in cross-border e-commerce transactions. It is currently unknown and requires additional empirical evidence whether or not international online commerce can reduce trade costs that are related to distance. There are also a great number of studies that investigate the effect that international online commerce has on the well-being of consumers from the perspectives of cost, cost of transaction, and the goods variety. According to the findings of an investigation by Consulting (2011) into the cross-border e-commerce of the European Union, consumers have saved a total of 12 billion euros as a result a plethora of choices, comparatively lower prices, and reduced search expenses. Lendle et al., (2012) estimated that the average increase in customer wellbeing would be a staggering 29% if costs associated with offline trade were brought down to the same level as those associated with online trade. Duch-Brown & Martens (2014) also estimated the gains to consumer welfare that would result from a reduction in the prices of goods traded across borders. In contrast, it is probable that consumers may diminish their welfare as a result of the heightened risks associated with online shopping, including those pertaining to the security of online transactions and the security of online delivery. Acquiring comprehensive information while shopping at brick-and-mortar stores that offer a wide range of products may require a significant investment of time and energy on the part of the consumer, particularly in comparison to the ease of online shopping. Hence, there is potential for e-commerce to reduce costs associated with both time and information while simultaneously increasing customer wellbeing (Martens, 2013). In addition to the studies that have been discussed above, a substantial amount of previous study has concentrated on aspects that have an impact on international online commerce. Cardona & Martens (2014) highlighted the problems that consumers and suppliers would experience

while attempting to trade something through cross-border electronic commerce channels. In research done by Van Heel et al., (2014), they believed that these barriers would eventually be removed by online retailers, carriers, and other service providers. The challenges encompass restricted visibility pertaining to delivery, hindrances in customs procedures, intricate and equivocal return protocols, and indeterminate pricing. The creation of a worldwide business will be facilitated by the expansion of cross-border e-commerce. Kawa & Zdrenka (2016) described the notion of an integrator in the realm of cross-border e-commerce as a viable remedy to the logistical obstacles encountered in this domain that are visible in cross-border e-commerce. This would be accomplished by combining the complete network of entities and activities involved in the production, distribution, and delivery of goods or services. Heikkurinen et al., (2013) investigated impact of logistics oversight on the enhancement of logistics systems in facilitating global e-commerce. The application of Kansei engineering and data mining methods was suggested as a means of providing a logistics service for international online business transactions from the perspective of end users (Hsiao et al., 2017). Zhou et al., (2016) developed a solution involving location and routing for the final mile of distribution for online businesses. A hybrid evolutionary search algorithm was developed through the integration of a genetic algorithm and a local search. This algorithm was based on a developmental investigation. The emergence of a new comparative advantage can be attributed to fluctuations in transaction costs. They discovered a new way to escape the traditional comparative advantage trap. This allowed them to escape the traditional comparative advantage trap. Kim et al., (2016) highlighted how important it is for online retailers to have thoughtfully developed delivery services in order to cut down on the distance between themselves and their international online consumers. They verified that an improvement in express delivery services is necessary for the continued expansion of international online commerce. As Oleynikova & Zorkin, (2016) presented, the sustainable growth of both the economy and society has been significantly aided by the increasing significance of the role played by network information technology. Because of this, government agencies and academic institutions are paying a growing amount of attention to the exponential expansion of international electronic commerce that has been made possible by advances in technology. It is necessary to conduct an analysis of the effects of international online commerce not only for the purpose of formulating the government's policies regarding international trade but also in terms of the

environmentally responsible growth of the economy. Nevertheless, the majority of the research that has been done thus far concentrates on analyzing the effects of international online commerce on trade distance and customer satisfaction. Because of this constraint, we feel compelled to conduct an empirical investigation into the effect that cross-border e-commerce has on international trade from the point of view of the economics of transaction costs.

1.1.3 E-commerce security

Before beginning the process of deploying a system for electronic commerce, it is imperative to initially tackle the diverse security issues that are associated with such a system and its primary components (Ladan, 2014). This is necessary in order to ensure the accessibility, viability, and safety of the data that is involved in the various types of transactions. A strike using a distributed denial of service (DDOS) can prevent hundreds of thousands or millions of customers from using an online shopping system. No one will do business with an e-commerce platform that has the potential to inadvertently disseminate sensitive customer information, including credit card numbers, personal data, banking details and account number. This is because such a platform would be vulnerable to a security breach. In an example that has been grossly oversimplified, a customer uses a website as part of an online shopping transaction and provides the website with their location and bank information. This relatively straightforward online transaction contains a number of possible security vulnerabilities that are connected to the various parts of the framework. These flaws are included in the forthcoming aspects of the system (Ladan, 2014):

- Security flaws in the context of client and home computers, it is possible for hostile websites to illicitly obtain and decipher data that is stored within a web "cookie". There exist viruses that can be transmitted through email and have the capability to extract sensitive financial information from the user's local disk; websites that are hostile to cookies.
- Surveillance and data theft in home wireless networks as a result of inadequate encryption measures or the absence of encryption protocols altogether.

- Surveillance and data theft from the keystrokes of customers using point-of-sale (POS) terminals are commonly utilized in conventional physical retail establishments are both illegal.
- Intercepting conversations and data theft from the mobile and handheld devices used by the user.
- Intercepting private conversations and stealing data from computer networks and other types of transitional links.

The firewall is the primary tool that companies rely on to protect the internal networks of their organizations. A firewall is a combination hardware and software system that restricts access to a protected network to only those users on the outside who match a certain set of criteria (Kalakota & Whinston, 1997).

Digital Equipment Cooperation (DEC) has the credit for developing the packet filtering firewalls in 1988. It only blocked packets from certain source IP addresses, not viruses or network threats. AT&T Bell Labs created the stateful firewall in 1990 to improve packet filtering networks. DEC developed the application gateway firewall in 1991 to detect network attacks as the internet grew. Web servers were protected by the web application firewall in 1997, which was successful at detecting network attacks (Liang & Kim, 2022).

Due to its fundamental capabilities, the packet filtering firewall is simple to configure and can filter packets effectively. However, the packet filtering firewall does not inspect the payload, which resides at the Open System Interconnection Model (OSI) application layer. Additionally, it does not authenticate users and is susceptible to IP spoofing (Wool, 2006).

The ability of the organization to protect users' privacy, authentic information, the system's integrity, and availability, as well as prevent unauthorized intrusions, is critical to the success of transaction security. Unauthorized network monitoring poses a potential risk to the confidentiality of transactions. The most common approach to ensuring one's privacy and confidentiality is through the use of encryption. To maintain the integrity of a transaction, it is necessary to implement safeguards that prevent the transaction from being altered in any way while it is being sent to or received from a customer (Kalakota & Whinston, 1997).

Another definition of e-commerce security is the practice of adhering to a set of rules and guidelines designed to ensure the secure conduct of all online financial transactions. These safeguarding standards must be implemented to ensure the safety of various e-commerce businesses from a wide variety of undeniable threats. Protecting financial data during online transactions is a crucial responsibility (Sengupta et al., 2005).

1.1.4 E-commerce marketing

Due to the low transaction volume and simplicity of the information involved in early e-commerce transactions, human experts were able to formulate basic rules based on relevant knowledge and experience, and these rules were subsequently incorporated into risk control engines. As a result, numerous conventional rule-based methods for detecting fraudulent financial activities have been developed over time (Panigrahi et al., 2009). For instance, using statistical analyses of users' past data regarding transaction times, transaction completion times, and night transactions, Dharwa & Patel, (2011) trained their rule-based models with feature engineering techniques. The effectiveness of rule-based methods, however, has been greatly diminished in recent years as the sophistication of e-commerce fraud has rapidly increased. As a result, data mining and machine learning-based fraud detection techniques have advanced rapidly in recent years (Xie et al., 2023).

Some studies, for instance Klepek & Kvíčala, (2022) advocate for a customer-centric marketing approach that places a premium on repeat business. Nevertheless, there is often a lack of standardized evidence or empirical data demonstrating a significant impact on key business indicators. Numerous studies on brand loyalty also rely on attitudinal information obtained from questionnaires; however, this information does not accurately capture brand loyalty and has a poor correspondence to actual shopping behavior (Naami et al., 2022). Therefore, the quality of attitudinal data is inherently lower than the quality of real behavioral data that is available in e-commerce. Even though extreme loyalty should help a company achieve higher levels of profitability, it is unclear how this trait will affect the company's market share. In contrast to these ideas, there is a body of research that advocates placing a significant emphasis on customer acquisition that is supported by field data. These data observations provide so-called empirical generalization. A

pattern or regularity that persists across a variety of conditions and that can be simply described using mathematical, graphic, or symbolic methods (Bass, 1995). The academic community has been advocating for the continual replication or extension of empirical generalizations (Ehrenberg, 1995; Sharp et al., 2017), as a result of the fact that this is essential in determining the circumstances under which theories do and do not hold (Wright & Kearns, 1998).

The concept of precision marketing has the potential to stimulate group thought and increase comprehension of the criteria that are applied during segmentation and positioning. The goal is to provide superior service to customers, which will in turn raise awareness of the products' marketability and result in increased revenue for the business (Liu, 2022). The effect of precision marketing can only be optimized to its full potential by developing individual sales strategies for each customer. Maintain as much control as you can over the outcomes and costs of communication, provide standards based on science, and steer clear of randomness. When attempting to predict the detection index system of multilabel systems, neural networks are a useful tool. The prediction model outperforms virtually all other prediction models that are currently available across almost all five performance indicators (Zhuo et al., 2020).

1.2 Online Shopping Intention

Numerous studies (e.g., Masoud, 2013; Özsürunc, 2017; Wai Tham et al., 2019) have been conducted previously to examine customer purchasing intention in terms of purchasing items online. These studies indicate that technological factors have an effect on consumer behavior. However, there are many studies conducted on buying decisions and the various factors that exert an influence on them. Previous studies indicate that cultural (Pantano, 2011), demographic (Luu et al., 2023), social (Luu et al., 2023), and other marketing-related factors (Trandafilovic & Blagojevic, 2017) influence consumer decisions. According to a study of (Chandra & Sinha, 2013) that was conducted in the district of Bhilai, persuasion is the most influential factor on consumer behavior regarding online shopping, perception as a component of the impact of notable psychological factors on the online consumer behavior, and experience-based information has the potential to influence future purchase decisions.

The purchasing decision of an individual is influenced by psychological factors such as attitude, beliefs, perception, learning, and motivation (Jain et al., 2015). The definition of attitude is a person's relatively consistent evaluations, feelings, and tendencies toward an object or concept. A study conducted by Osman et al., (2010) on Malaysian university participants to determine their online buying behaviors reveals that the majority of students' decisions are influenced by their perception, which in turn influences their attitude. Pricing perceptions play a significant role in decision-making (Jain et al., 2015).

Shopping intention is the likelihood that a consumer will make a purchase decision to buy a product or to go to a store that provides a service to customers in the near future (Grewal et al., 1998). The extent to which a consumer is willing to make a purchase of a product or service is typically referred to as their shopping intention. Purchases are an extremely important factor in the expansion of sales for companies (J. Shim et al., 2021). It is essential to have a good understanding of consumers' intentions to make purchases because this relates to consumers' actions, perceptions, and attitudes; additionally, consumer purchasing attitude can be studied (Heijden et al., 2003).

The concept of shopping intention refers to the extent to which a consumer is inclined to make a purchase of an item in particular, and purchases are one of the most important factors in the sales growth and market share of any company (Alalwan, 2018). As a result, academics have looked into the concept of shopping intent. For instance, Wang, (2014) conducted a study on the precursors of purchase inclination within the realm of brand administration. The precursors of the study were risk, value, and quality. When Dehghani and Tumer (2015) evaluated the effect of Facebook advertising, one of the dependent variables they used was consumers' intentions to make a purchase. The study conducted by (Rana & Paul, 2017) focused on natural products and utilized purchase intention as the explanatory feature. The study's results indicate that health is a noteworthy factor to consider when assessing intent to buy. Hsiao & Chen (2018) carried out a study in order to take into consideration the buying intention of potential smart watch customers. In his investigation into the impact of green marketing, Mohd Suki (2016) focused primarily on consumers' propensities to make purchases as the primary variable.

1.2.1. Purchasing online perspective

The acquisition and formation of attitudes occur through a process of learning and development, which can be resistant to modification but may be subject to alteration through the fulfillment of psychological incentives, as posited by (Lien & Cao, 2014). According to Shaouf et al., (2016), attitudes undergo a transformation over time as individuals acquire novel insights pertaining to the notion or entity they are assessing. According to Fishbein & Ajzen, (1977), the construct of attitude refers to an individual's evaluative judgment, whether positive or negative, of a particular attitude. In their research, Andrews & Bianchi, (2013) they believed that attitude was understood as the consumer's assessment of purchasing through online stores. As per the findings of Amaro & Duarte, (2015), intentions are a consequence of the attitude towards a specific act. Specifically, a more favorable attitude towards a behavior is associated with a higher likelihood of intending to engage in that conduct.

1.2.2 Personal standards

Personal standards refer to an individual's perception of appropriate or inappropriate behavior based on the potential rewards or punishments associated with such actions. The study conducted by Kim et al., (2013) defines personal standards as the impetus that a consumer receives from their social network, including friends, family, and colleagues, to engage in online shopping activities. The construct of personal standards is frequently employed as a precursor to decision-making, as individuals are more likely to engage in a particular behavior if their role models endorse it. This phenomenon has been documented in prior research (Sandve & Ogaard, 2014; Schepers & Wetzels, 2007). According to Nor & Pearson, (2008) research, personal standards originating from social circles, including friends, family, and colleagues, exert a favorable impact on online purchasing behavior. As per the earlier literature, it is posited that the inclination of consumers towards making online purchases is likely to increase if they perceive that their peers hold a favorable view towards the same. The available evidence suggests that cultural background has a significant impact on the subjective perceptions of consumers. The degree of individualism can serve as a determinant for the influence of national culture on interpersonal connections within the examined areas. According to Schepers &

Wetzels, (2007), the behavioral intention of consumers is influenced by personal standards, which are based on perceived social pressure. Individuals who place importance on personal standards tend to conform to the expectations of their peers. According to Choi & Geistfeld, (2004), it is anticipated that individuals in collectivist cultures will exhibit more pronounced personal standards compared to those in individualistic cultures in order to gain acceptance from the group.

1.2.3 Perceived usefulness

As per the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) proposed by Agag & El-Masry, (2016), the acceptance of an IT is determined by various cognitive factors, among which perceived usefulness holds significant importance. According to Lee, (2009), the term pertains to an individual's conviction regarding the enhancement of their performance and productivity through the utilization of novel technology. Davis, (1989) introduced the concept that individuals are more likely to adopt information technology (IT) if they perceive that it will enhance their performance. The concept of perceived usefulness in e-commerce has been examined with regards to the consumer's perception of the efficacy, efficiency, and significance of electronic retail outlets. According to Perea Y Monsuwé et al., (2004), the concept of usefulness in e-commerce is contingent upon the post-purchase perceptions of consumers. Specifically, usefulness is defined as the extent to which consumers perceive that online shopping will enhance every aspect of their purchasing experiences can be achieved by enhancing various aspects of the process. It is anticipated that enhancing the outcome of the shopping experience in an online store will lead to a favorable evaluation of e-commerce by the consumer. Furthermore, as per Hofstede, (2011) research, indulgence refers to the extent to which individuals attempt to regulate their impulses and cravings for personal gratification. According to Belanche Gracia et al., (2015), a society with high levels of indulgence tends to prioritize pleasure and entertainment.

1.2.4 Online and offline shopping

The examination of consumer behavior in "offline" or "traditional" settings can serve as a basis for exploring consumer behavior in "online" or "virtual" contexts to a considerable extent. Various general frameworks in the field of consumer behavior are presently accessible to capture the decision-making processes of consumers, as noted by Schiffman & Kanuk, (2000). Various models have been developed to

differentiate between several stages of the consumer decision-making process. The most prevalent stages include the stage of recognizing the need, the stage of conducting a pre-purchase search, the stage of evaluating alternatives, the stage of making the actual purchase, and the stage of evaluating the purchase after it has been made. The aforementioned stages exhibit a considerable level of abstraction and do not duly consider the specific channel employed by the consumer to effectuate their purchase. According to O'Keefe & McEachern, (1998), the phases are relevant to the conduct of online shoppers. When we compare the shopping behaviors of people who do their shopping online with those who do their shopping in traditional brick-and-mortar stores, we can identify at least two distinct categories of differences between the two types of customers. To begin, customers who shop for goods and services online are required to engage in conversations with various pieces of technology. An electronic shopping environment, or, to put it another way, an information system, has taken the place of the traditional brick-and-mortar store environment (IS). This results in the emergence of technical issues that have historically been the purview of researchers in information systems (IS) and human computer interaction (HCI) (O'Keefe et al., 2000).

Furthermore, a higher level of trust is required when making purchases in an online environment compared to when making purchases in a traditional store. It is common knowledge at this point that those who engage in online business face the challenge of maintaining their customers' trust (Keen et al., 1999). When the quality of the product is unknown, the shop owners are unknown, the shop's location is unknown, and the performance of the settlement is unknown, feelings of uncertainty can become exacerbated. However, trust can help alleviate these feelings (Yao-Hua Tan, 2000). These circumstances almost certainly will manifest themselves within the context of e-commerce.

There have been a number of studies conducted in recent years that investigate customer propensity to purchase online as a result of the widespread emergence of e-commerce platforms and the emergence of the web. There is also some evidence to support the idea that individuals exhibit a concern not solely for the utilitarian benefits afforded by technological advancements, but also for the experiential and pleasurable benefits they offer (Childers et al., 2001).

Many studies (Mokhtarian, 1990; Salomon, 1986) have been done on the impact that online shopping has had on traditional shopping trips, and the findings can typically be categorized into one of four categories: replacement, collaboration, reconfiguration, as well as neutrality (Edrisi et al., 2020). In this context, the term "substitution" refers to the process by which in-store purchasing has supplanted online shopping, which has, in turn, reduced the number of times that individuals go shopping. E-shopping can lead to an increase in consumers' demand for in-person trips, according to the complementary mode of operation. In such an instance, the term "modification" pertains to the notion that despite the availability of online shopping, consumers are still required to undertake tangible journeys, but those certain aspects of the trip, such as the amount of time spent traveling, can be affected. A neutrality test determines whether or not online shopping influences in-store shopping (Edrisi et al., 2020).

So far, there have been a great number of studies (Chiu et al., 2005; H. H. Lee et al., 2006; Pan, 2010; Vellido et al., 2000a) done on the factors that influence the intention to shop online, including convenience, perceived pleasure, perceived utility, perceived risk, and security information, which are often taken into consideration in academic research. In accordance with (Donthu & Garcia, 1999), customers who shop online are searching for ease and diversity, and they are also much more likely to experience new technologies than customers who shop in stores (Jarvenpaa et al., 2000). In addition, the credibility of the shopping platform and the level of perceived trust were considered as aspects that influence the attitudes of online shoppers. Vellido et al., (2000) looked at nine different impacts that have an effect on people's decisions to shop online. It was found that the primary determinant that exerted an adverse influence on an individual's intent to shop online was their perception of the level of risk involved in doing so. Furthermore, according to Siu & Cheng, (2001) assertion, the primary consideration for customers engaging in online shopping is the economic advantages it offers. The decision regarding which method of buying products may be influenced by factors beyond the categorization and pricing of goods, such as the personal motivation of the buyer. According to the findings of Hernández et al., (2010), the influence of convenience was found to be insignificant among individuals who exhibited a willingness to experiment with online shopping for the first time. In a separate study conducted in 2011, the authors reported that variables such as age,

gender, and income were found to be significant factors on the behaviors of experienced online shoppers (Hernández et al., 2011). Likewise, Kee & Wan (2004) discovered that a customer's gender as well as their level of education could significantly influence their intention to shop online. Y. Pan et al., (2010) also found that convenience exerted a greater influence on individuals' inclination to engage in online shopping as compared to demographic attributes, personal standards, and perception factors. Moreover, Pérez-Hernández & Sánchez-Mangas (2011) indicated that effective access to the Internet at home could result in a 14% increase in consumers' intention to shop online.

1.2.5 Shopping orientation aspects

It was discovered that social factors, specifically the influence of reference groups, have a significant impact on the consumer decision-making process. The reference group consists of family, friends, and peers who exert a substantial influence on the consumer decision-making process. According to a study conducted by Abadi et al., (2011) on Iranian students, social impact has a significant effect on online purchasing behavior. Particularly if a person observes that his friends, family members, and relatives are using online shopping, he or she can easily adopt the practice. According to a study conducted on Malaysian government employees and servants by Chin et al., (2009), social influence has a positive effect on consumer purchases and online trust. Perceived behavioral control refers to the availability of resources necessary to perform a specific behavior. MBA students' perceptions of the exertion of behavioral control was found to have a noteworthy influence on the online consumer attitudes (Al-Swidi et al., 2012). In a separate study conducted by Javadi et al. (2012) on Iranian consumers, attitude and perceived behavioral control were found to be positively associated with online purchase behavior, prior knowledge and perspective. Experience plays a crucial role in influencing the decision-making process, and perception of pricing is another important factor. In a study conducted by L. Lin and Chen (2006), product knowledge and product involvement were found to be significantly related to consumers' choices.

The consumer expresses his desire for a specific product through a decision issued by him/her that translates into either buying the product or abstaining from it. One of the most important purchase steps is the purchase decision-making process for

the consumer. This stage means the acquisition of the product and subjecting it to experimentation in order to satisfy the needs and desires. The most important basics of purchasing decision-making by the consumer will be discussed, which is an important step to determining consumer behavior towards the risks of e-commerce. The online pre-purchase intentions framework by S. Shim et al. (2001) identified a link between the intent to use online services for information seeking and the plan to use them for purchases. People who intend to browse websites probably also intend to shop online. According to Kline, (2015) customers will select the most affordable option while looking for and acquiring products and services; searching and buying through one source, like the web, could be seen as cheaper than searching and buying through several sources.

Moreover, Dijst et al., (2008) demonstrated that people with a significant level of expertise in the realm of online technology were more likely to engage in online shopping. Along with that, it's possible that using credit cards will make people more likely to go ahead and make purchases online. Keisidou et al., (2011) explored the attitudes of individuals and how those attitudes affected their online shopping for a variety of goods. Schmid & Axhausen, (2019) looked into the pros and cons of shopping online versus shopping in physical stores for home appliances and food items. Similarly, Crocco et al., (2013) asserted that certain aspects of online shopping, such as a wider selection of products, easier access to more detailed information, the ability to take advantage of discounts, and the ability to easily compare prices, could contribute to an increase in online shopping. Features of the website, ease of use, product variety, and the availability of consumer resources may all have a positive influence on the intent to make an online purchase (Clemes et al., 2014). The selection of this shopping method may be impeded by various factors, such as perceived risk, service quality, and personal standards. Hasbullah et al., (2016) also examined the impact of certain aspects on e-shopping intention. These variables included website usability, attitudes, and subjective norms, the availability of items, competitive pricing, ancillary services associated with products, convenient comparison of product offerings and prices, and temporal attitudes and their significance were the primary factors that Jadhav & Khanna, (2016) identified as having an effect on e-shopping. Other factors included attitudes toward time and its value. Nevertheless, according to Ghouri et al. (2017), consumers' online shopping intentions were positively affected

by their previous e-shopping experiences, their levels of perceived trust, and their propensity to make unplanned purchases.

1.2.6 Online shopping addict

The widespread adoption of innovation and the swift progression of the web have facilitated the ability of online consumers to surmount the limitations associated with traditional shopping. This enables consumers to make purchases at their convenience, regardless of time or location. Furthermore, the widespread availability of wireless networks and advanced mobile devices has considerably enhanced the ability to shop online (Tang et al., 2014).

Concurrently with this tendency, more and more people are shopping online. The number of people shopping online has been steadily climbing over the past few years. According to the findings of the Survey on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Turkiye, in 2022, it was observed that 94.1% of households had internet access, while in the previous year, this percentage was 92% (TUIK, 2022).

According to the Turkish Statistical Institute, the percentage of people aged 16 to 74 who ordered or purchased goods or services for private use over the internet increased to 44.3 % in 2021 from a previous year's figure of 36.5%. In 2021, this percentage was higher than the previous year's figure of 36.5 % (*Figure -1*). When broken down by gender, males made up 48.3 percent of those who ordered or purchased goods or services over the internet, while females made up only 40.3 percent of this group. The previous year's findings showed that this proportion was 40.2%, while the respective value for the other was 32.7%. When the most recent time period to purchase or order goods or services for private purposes over the Internet is taken into consideration, the rate of those declaring as of the first quarter of 2021 was 32.4 percent. When compared to the same time period the year before, this rate was 23.9% (TUIK, 2021b).

Figure 1-Online shoppers in Türkiye

Along with the expansion of the internet shopping sector, problems linked to it have seen an increase in prevalence. Problems stemming from online shopping, such as compulsive shopping and shopping addiction, have been conceptualized in the psychological literature (Andreassen et al., 2015). Even though there are a few different ways of conceptualizing it, it seems as though there are some consistent characteristics of online shopping addiction (Savci et al., 2021a). Authors such as According to (Griffiths, 2005) hypothesis, there are several shared characteristics among various types of addictions. According to the conception developed by (Marks, 1990), online shopping can be categorized as a form of addictive conduct. Trotzke et al., (2015) considered compulsive purchasing online to be a subtype of addiction to the web, which is itself a subtype of addiction in behavior. Addictive behaviors are medical issues that are characterized by the occurrence of recurring behaviors that have a negative impact on the lives of the individuals who suffer from them (Vilella et al., 2011). Both drug addiction and behavioral disorders share similarities in various aspects (Grant et al., 2010). There are many similarities between the mechanisms of addiction to substances and addictions to other things. Certain individuals are observed to be investing an inordinate amount of time in the pursuit of a particular activity while also exhibiting repeated efforts to curtail or discontinue said activity without achieving the desired outcome, having less control over the behavior, becoming tolerant of the behavior, withdrawing from the behavior, and experiencing negative psychosocial consequences (Grant et al., 2010; Griffiths, 2005).

Because people who indulge in compulsive internet shopping have desires, it is obvious that compulsive online shopping may be defined as a sort of addiction that is not tied to drug or behavior misuse (Trotzke et al., 2015). The term "online shopping addiction" has been defined in a variety of ways, but there is no universally

accepted definition for the term. According to the findings of research that was carried out on shopping addiction, there is a connection between shopping addiction and psychiatric disorders (Volpe et al., 1989).

1.2.7 Shopping habits

The cultural, social, and economic circumstances of an area all influence the shopping motivations of consumers (Tauber, 1972). Numerous research has been carried to investigate how consumers shop in relation to their attitudes, decision-making processes, and other Sprotles & Kendall (1986) developed a classification system for consumers based on the types of decisions they made. According to one definition, a consumer's decision-making style is "a mental orientation that characterizes the consumer's approach to making choices" (Sprotles & Kendall, 1986). Shoppers are categorized as per their habits based on their shopping styles (Lastovicka, 1982), perceptions and styles of product utilization (McCarty et al., 2007), characteristics of identity (Darden & Ashton, 1974), as well as orientation for shopping (Cowart & Goldsmith, 2007; Fan & Xiao, 1998). According to Myers and Nicosia (1968), consumer patterns ought to take into account desires, degrees of neglect, levels of social class, and identity aspects. The fundamental cognitive characteristics that impact the process of decision-making were identified by (Sprotles & Kendall, 1986). The aforementioned traits encompass a tendency towards perfectionism or a heightened awareness of quality, a proclivity towards brand awareness, a predilection for novelty or fashion, a preference for recreational or hedonistic pursuits, a consideration for price and value for money, a tendency towards impulsivity, and a sense of confusion stemming from an abundance of choices, and being loyal to a habit or brand. According to the findings presented by Shocker et al. (1991), various decision-making models will be required depending on the context of the decision. The availability of alternative products has an effect on the buyer's behavior. There are some products for which the set of available options might only include a singular alternative. This phenomenon could be observed in the context of commodities that are either characterized by high cost, low frequency of purchase, or are perceived as experiential in nature. (Sprotles & Kendall, 1986) developed the Consumer Style Inventory (CSI), the adaptation of this approach has facilitated the examination of consumer decision-making processes across diverse cultural contexts. The CSI was modified by Lysonski et al. (1996) in order to determine profiles of

consumer decision-making, they imply that the utilization of CSI appears to be more prevalent in developed nations, than it was in less developed countries. Consumers exhibited a variety of buying patterns due to the fact that the cultural and economic environments in which they shopped varied. Differences between countries may be attributed to factors such as the non-availability of brands, the absence of organized retail formats, and inadequate infrastructure. It was suggested that the CSI scale should be modified for use in developing countries. In their research on the applicability of the CSI to Chinese consumers, Fan & Xiao, (1998) utilized an altered version of the instrument. Among Chinese consumers, essential buying habits included paying attention to brands, prices, quality, timing, and information when making purchases. The findings were analyzed in relation to the shopping habits of consumers in both Korea and the United States. It was clear that consumers in various countries share similar characteristics. Differences between consumer groups can be attributed to factors such as the level of development of consumer markets, levels of purchasing power, and cultural norms.

1.3 Online Perceived Risk

The concept of risk is subject to varying interpretations among individuals, as posited by (Slovic, 1987). This phenomenon has significantly contributed to the delineation and advancement of the term “risk”. The term “risk” was initially introduced into the English lexicon during the 16th century (Grima et al., 2021), and subsequently underwent a transformation from its French origin “risqué” to its current form, as documented by Rey-Debove & Lebeau-Bensa, (1995). According to Grima & Bezzina, (2018), when the term “risqué” is translated into the term "rescare" in Latin is associated with the action of cutting, it acquires a pejorative implication. A sentiment that aligns with the unfavorable views expressed in Grima & Bezzina, (2018) work. Risk was also defined by Haimes, (2009) as "a measure of the probability and severity of adverse effects”.

The term "perceived risk" was introduced by Bauer, (1960), according to scholarly sources. The author posits that the outcome of the consumer's choice is unpredictable and that a portion of these outcomes are likely to be unfavorable. The objective of perceived risk theory is to comprehend consumer behavior by solving issues regarding consumer choice (Pi & Sangruang, 2011a). Fields (1987) defines

perceived risk as consumers' emotional state when making decisions in uncertain situations. When a customer's mind is unclear regarding online purchasing, they cannot be certain whether to shop online or not. This uncertainty causes buyers to feel a high level of risk, and they believe their purchasing decision may not be accurate (Goodwin, 2009).

In earlier research, risk evaluations were modeled as distributive models, which utilize distribution instances and their corresponding modifications. As potential factors that can determine risk judgments, expected value, variance, skewness, range, and frequency play has been repeated have all been investigated (Coombs, 1969). The paper by Coombs (1969) provided backing for a distributive model that relies on a specific configuration of the collective impact of said transformations on the perception of risk. The author considered several composition functions of three indices corresponding to transitions on multiple lotto. Barron (1976) did, however, find evidence that contradicted his assumptions about how such a distributive model works. According to the findings of a study that was conducted by Coombs and Lehner (1981), a polynomial distributive model that is simplistic in nature and encompasses variables that gauge the overall attributes of a distribution, such as expectation, dispersion, and asymmetry, is insufficient in accurately depicting perceived risk as a result of the intricate interactions that transpire among these variables. In simple words, Malapane, (2019) defined the risk as the process of acquiring commodities or amenities via the Web with significant hazards that consumers encounter frequently. Consumers encounter perceived risks that give rise to uncertainty in their purchasing decisions when considering the acquisition of goods or services through online channels. The aforementioned risks have an impact on the consumer's decision-making process, as they introduce elements of doubt that are difficult to avoid for a significant portion of individuals who engage in online shopping. The risks associated with online shopping are variable and cannot be disregarded, as they have the potential to undermine the level of service that customers anticipate. Additional hazards encompass non-receipt of online-purchased commodities or services, procurement of counterfeit merchandise via online channels, cost-effectiveness, and sundry other concerns. The aforementioned risks exert a substantial influence on the process of making decisions of numerous prospective

online shoppers who harbor doubts and exhibit a lack of confidence in e-commerce establishments.

Later in this chapter, additional discussion of each type of risk incorporated into this research is provided. The following is a brief definition of the discussed types of risks:

1. Financial risk is the potential expenditures associated with the initial purchase price and subsequent maintenance of the product, as well as the potential monetary loss resulting from fraud. In other words, the probability of incurring a financial loss as a result of hidden costs, maintenance expenses, or a lack of warranty in the event of defects (Sharma & Das, 2017).
2. Quality risk identifies the likelihood that a purchased product will not function as expected. In other words, the risk that the product will malfunction and fail to perform as intended and advertised, thereby failing to deliver the expected benefits (Sharma & Das, 2017).
3. Delivery risk has been defined by Ariff et al., (2014) as the possibility of delivery failure resulting from factors such as lost goods, damaged goods, and incorrect delivery location after confirmation of an online order.

The varying prevalence of risk factors in different purchasing scenarios implies that the significance of different risk dimensions may not be uniform across all purchase intentions. The act of getting a haircut is associated with heightened social visibility, consequently, this enhances the probability of encountering psychological or social risks. However, the probability of experiencing physical risks during a haircut is relatively low. In contrast, banking services entail heightened risks with respect to both temporal and financial aspects. The identified facets of perceived risk have predominantly been explored in relation to product procurement without necessarily considering the context in which the procurement occurs (Lin et al., 2009). Moreover, a number of studies show that customers have varying perceptions of risk depending on the mode of shopping they engage in. For instance, it is observed that customers tend to perceive a greater level of risk when making purchases through mail order channels in comparison to shopping at brick-and-mortar retail establishments (Spence et al., 1970). In a similar vein, Cox and Rich (1964) observed that there is a prevalent

perception among individuals that the level of risk associated with telephone shopping is higher in comparison to in-store shopping. This is due to the fact that telephone shopping does not provide customers with the chance to physically interact with or experiment with a particular item before making a purchase. Therefore, it is not unreasonable to suggest that the risks that are normally associated with shopping online might also be increased.

1.3.1 Risk-relievers

As per Roselius, (1971) findings, a risk-mitigating measure refers to any course of action undertaken by a purchaser or vendor with the intention of minimizing the perceived risk. Throughout history, there has been a prevalent belief and acceptance that a positive correlation exists between consumers' perceived level of risk exposure and their demand for risk-reducing measures; that is, the more risk that consumers believe they are exposed to, the greater their demand for risk-reducers will be (Derbaix, 1983). Since perceived risk is seen to have ambiguity and repercussions (Bauer, 1960), it makes sense that the perceived level of risk could be brought down to a more "acceptable" level by using one or both of the following strategies: making it more likely that the loss won't happen, or making it less bad when it does. Researchers have proposed a wide variety of risk-relievers in an effort to reduce the perceived risk.

The work of Roselius (1971) served as the foundation for a great deal of subsequent research on risk-reducers. He highlighted a number of factors that reduced the likelihood of negative outcomes, such as recommendation, brand devotion, private product testing, brand image, store image, and the availability of free samples, refund assurances, shopping, expensive models, and a good phrase. Derbaix (1983) offered his own additional risk-reduction plan—a salesman's recommendation. Similar risk-reducers were suggested by Greatorex and Mitchell (1994), including buying a less expensive brand, taking advantage of special deals, reading package information, and subscribing to consumer publications. It should be highlighted that most risk-reducers work to raise the likelihood that the end result will be satisfactory rather than lessen the impact of failure. To put it another way, care was taken to increase the prepurchase effectiveness of risk-relievers (Derbaix, 1983). Two researches (Tan, 1999; Van den Poel & Leunis, 1999) notably take into account the circumstances

of online buying when examining risk-reliever preferences. With the exception of payment security, which is a distinct feature of online transactions, it seems that the other methods of risk reduction are comparable to those that have been previously recognized for traditional shopping scenarios. In the realm of consumer behavior, it has been observed that many of the risk-mitigating strategies that are commonly employed in the context of in-person retail transactions can also be effectively utilized in the realm of e-commerce. One could posit that despite alterations in the mode of articulation, the fundamental characteristics of the risk mitigator persist. Despite its widespread use as a risk mitigation strategy in conventional purchasing scenarios, the virtual communities present on specific websites represent a distinctive form of positive endorsement that is specific to this relatively novel platform. This suggests that it is advisable for customers to seek guidance from acquaintances, relatives, or fellow travelers in virtual travel communities prior to finalizing a transaction.

Perceived risk refers to the degree of unexpected discomfort and frustration experienced in relation to purchasing decisions that are influenced by the intended target (Wai et al., 2019). It is widely acknowledged that online risk poses a significant roadblock to the expansion of online stores (Lăzăroiu et al., 2020). The risk associated with online shopping refers to the perception among consumers that they may encounter unfavorable and unpredictable outcomes (Wang et al., 2019). One of the characteristics of online risk is the unconventional method of payment, in which the buyer and the seller never actually meet one another in person. This circumstance lends credence to the idea that the act of shopping online exposes consumers to certain dangers that are unique to the medium. Concerns about the delivery and return of the item, as well as a lack of direct physical contact, are among these risks (Zhu et al., 2018). Being a target of fraudulent activity (Saxena et al., 2018), or being exposed to a virus on a computer (Indiani & Fahik, 2020).

Many people view financial dealings conducted online as more precarious than their traditional counterparts (Abyad, 2017), despite the fact that the feeling of danger decreases in proportion to the amount of time spent online (Yoon et al., 2019). Therefore, although users' awareness of the risks associated with online shopping may grow as they gain more Internet experience, this might not appear to be a barrier to consumers' willingness to use the platform.

Alkailani & Abu-Shanab (2021) found that customers frequently develop a sense of uneasiness when considering making purchases online due to the perception of potential dangers. Specifically, a number of studies have investigated the connection between the risks of shopping online and people's propensity to do so. For instance, Wai et al., (2019) investigated the influence that factors such as product, delivery, non-return policy, and financial flexibility have on consumers' propensity to purchase in Malaysia. Wai Tham et al., (2019) examined three factors that have a significant impact on consumers' decisions to shop online: product risk, return policy risk, and convenience risk. Likewise, Habib & Hamadneh, (2021) investigated the relationship between perceived risk and the intention to make a purchase online. These findings indicated that the level of risk that customers believe they are exposed to plays a significant role in determining whether or not they will buy things online.

Although the influence of perceived risk on online shopping is discussed, it has not yet been determined which types of perceived risk have the most significant effect on online shopping. According to Bhatnagar and Ghose (2004); Lu et al., (2005), there is a significant and negative impact on online purchase intent caused by product and financial risks. The investigation of Bhatnagar and Ghose (2004) pertains to the examination of consumer search behavior within the context of online retailing, asserting that there is a significant impact that product risk has on online shopping due to the fact that customers cannot obtain adequate product information online.

Eggert (2006) discovered that the risk of invasion of privacy had a more significant impact on online shopping than the risk of purchasing a defective product. In her study, Dai (2007) reveals that customers' intent to shop online for various product categories is influenced by three different types of perceived risk: product, financial, and privacy concerns. Customers may determine the likelihood of unfavorable outcomes for a number of perceived risks, such as those related to their finances, health, social lives, or performance (Goodwin, 2009). Performance, time, and social risk are more significant to customers than privacy and security risk, according to Almousa (2014); Thakur & Srivastava (2015) conducted research on Arabian consumers and came to the conclusion that the privacy risk component of online shopping is the most significant factor affecting it, followed by the financial risk component as the second most significant factor among the six dimensions identified.

After a comprehensive literature review, Al-Rawad et al., (2015) have come to the conclusion that the perceived financial risk and the operational risk are the two most significant risk factors associated with online shopping, while the social risk is the least significant. Gozukara et al. (2014) conducted an empirical study and found that customer perception of risk moderates the relationship between hedonistic motivation and purchase behavior.

The convenience of shopping online Consumers shop for goods and services using e-commerce platforms to complete their transactions online. This method is similar to traditional approaches to shopping in that it consists of several steps. According to Huang et al., (2004), customers who shop from their homes or offices in person are more technically vulnerable than customers who shop online. The dependability of web sources is contingent upon several factors, including the acceptance of orders, the provision of prompt responses, the maintenance of on-time delivery, and the protection of personal information pertaining to customers. Users who shop online make use of the internet to locate, choose, buy, utilize, and handle both services and products that are tailored to their requirements. When people visit websites and conduct business online, they expose themselves to a number of risks. When compared to shopping in a traditional store, the level of risk that customers face when making purchases online is significantly higher (Lee & Tan, 2003). According to the findings of previous studies, the most important factor that motivates people to shop online is convenience, followed by the ability to save time, a greater variety of products and services, and feeling less pressure from salespeople (McQuitty & Peterson, 2000).

When consumers order goods that are not sold in their neighborhood stores online, they do not have to be concerned about factors such as parking, traffic, or climate. Yet, concerns regarding customer cybercrime and the security of sensitive data provided by customers are emerging as e-commerce continues to grow. Consumers need to avoid excessive transfers of personal information and reduce the sharing of personal information that is unnecessary (S. Wang et al., 2021).

The stakes involved in the shopping decision and the person's sense of internal conviction about whether they are "winning" or "losing" the entire amount involved in the transaction are two key variables that influence the perceived level of risk by a customer. The level of risk that a customer perceives is dependent on these two key

variables. It also describes the likelihood of customers making poor selections while they are in the process of shopping. In addition to the possibility of having a negative reaction to a product after evaluating it in relation to the customer's expectations (Zheng et al., 2012). A powerful indicator of consumer behavior is referred to as perceived risk. This is due to the fact that buyers are more likely to seek the accomplishment of their purchases than they are to reduce the potential for their purchases to fail. A measure of unexpected dissatisfaction and frustration with purchasing decisions based on the purchase aim is called perceived risk (Mitchell, 1999). According to Mohd Satar et al. (2019), in the majority of cases, successful e-commerce transactions are the result of active online purchasing activity. When it comes to online shopping, consumers' perceptions of risk are influenced by a number of different factors.

Reliability has been recognized as one of the most essential qualities, particularly with regard to online shopping. Online shopping is considered to be fraught with danger for customers because there is no opportunity for face-to-face interaction or direct communication with the retail establishment or its employees (Alharthey, 2020). Earlier studies have focused their attention on a particular facet of online consumption that is referred to as "shopping orientation". According to Childers et al., (2001) it is possible to divide customers who shop online into two distinct groups: those who do so for the purpose of entertainment and those who do so for practical reasons. Previous studies have been conducted to investigate both of these types of consumer behavior (Chiders et al., 2001). Consumers save time, have easier access to service information, are more likely to seek information, and are less likely to be engaged in conversation with salespeople when they shop online, all of which contribute to an increased sense of convenience (Zhou et al., 2007).

1.3.2 Perceived financial risk and online shopping intention:

There is a significant rise in the number of people shopping online, and there is reason to be optimistic about the industry's future growth prospects; however, there are some downsides to this trend that are becoming more prevalent. The lack of security that exists online, particularly when it comes to using credit cards and revealing personal information, is a source of concern for customers. The concept of "financial risk" refers to the presumption that a particular amount of money may be

lost or may be required for a product to operate as intended. Furthermore, it is defined as a possible loss in net financial value and takes into account the consumer's sense of unease while using a credit card online, which research has shown to be a significant barrier to making online transactions (Masoud, 2013). Customers who place orders online still prefer to pay with methods other than credit cards, such as cash upon delivery, electronic transfer services, and third-party secured transactions through websites like PayPal (Wai Tham et al., 2019). Previous research has shown that one of the most common concerns customers have when making purchases online is the possibility of credit card fraud (Saprikis et al., 2010). Consumers who opt to shop online give serious consideration to the possibility of incurring financial loss before deciding whether or not to make purchases. The reason for this situation is the emergence of financial risks that pose a potential danger, which in turn has influenced perceptions and altered the intentions of customers. As can be deduced from Wilson et al.'s study (2016), it is common for there to be a financial risk involved in the very first phase of online shopping, which is immediately following the buyer's web-based purchase.

Previous studies in the field of credit card marketing and consumer behavior have covered topics concerning the exploration of strategies and approaches to address the state of saturation in credit card sectors. There have been researches conducted to identify and analyze the usage patterns of consumers as well as to investigate the myriad of opportunities available to grow and expand the credit card business. As a result of the nearly complete penetration of the Asian and Hispanic markets in the United States, consumers were recognized based on the patterns of credit card usage they displayed when making rent payments, purchasing clothing and shoes. This allowed for the identification of a potential opportunity (Delener & Katzenstein, 1994). Because the credit card market is maturing, it was necessary to identify the promotion tactics which can be employed to introduce attraction cards and offer value-added features, including frequent user programs. The purpose of this action was to maintain the current customer base and to entice prospective clients (Duffy, 1990).

The term "financial risk" refers to the possibility that the actual cost of online shopping will be higher than the amount that was planned for expenditures. The same procedures must be followed in order to manage financial risk as are required for managing general risk. These procedures include determining the factors that pose a

risk, evaluating that risk, and formulating strategies to mitigate it. There is a potential for monetary loss either due to the theft of credit card numbers by cybercriminals or the misuse of credit card information by the intended recipients (Pi & Sangruang, 2011b). Therefore, drawing from the aforementioned explanations and based on the previously supported hypothesis of Wai T et al., 2019, the subsequent hypothesis can be posited:

H1: Financial risk has a negative impact on consumers' online shopping intention.

1.3.3 Perceived quality risk and online shopping intention:

Similar to traditional shopping, online shopping poses challenges in terms of evaluating tangible goods, as consumers are constrained to rely on limited visual aids and product descriptions. The concept of quality risk pertains to the likelihood of a procured item failing to meet expected performance standards. And the loss incurred when a brand or product does not perform as anticipated is largely attributable to the inability of online shoppers to conduct a precise evaluation of the product's quality (Masoud, 2013). The term quality risk pertains to the level of implementation or standard of the products and services that consumers opt for when making online purchases. Alreck & Settle, (2002) have identified that the risk associated with quality can be classified into various categories based on the type of client. Crespo et al., (2009) posited that financial loss represents a risk that is linked to products, as it engenders apprehension among consumers that deception may be at play, thereby exposing them to the possibility of incurring financial losses.

The concept of quality risk pertains to the variation between the real risk of a product and the risk that was initially projected during the product's modeling phase. The product's depiction and portrayal have a substantial influence on consumers' comprehension of the merchandise, thereby generating a quality risk. Insufficient presentation of item details and the incapacity to conduct an examination of an item may elicit a sense of unease among consumers. Typically, quality risk pertains to the procurement of goods that may fail to function according to their intended specifications (Kim, 2010). According to certain studies, Sharma & Das, (2017), the possibility of encountering product or performance risks in the online milieu is becoming increasingly worrisome, as concerns regarding malfunctioning or subpar

performance of items are on the rise. To summarize, a significant apprehension when engaging in online shopping is the incapacity to physically touch, examine, or obtain a sample of the product prior to purchase. According to Saprikis et al., (2010), concerns of this nature have the potential to elevate the likelihood of suboptimal quality or performance.

Both "quality" and "quality cost" can be understood in a number of different ways. We can use the phrase "the product attributes for which consumers prefer more to less" as its definition of quality (Kaya & Özer, 2009 p.671). This definition is very similar to the definition that is based on the user in Garvin & Quality, (1984) designation. According to this definition, quality is related to the satisfaction of customers as well as the capability of the product for its intended use. The performance quality of a product is determined by its ability to function properly and its physical characteristics in order to fulfill the requirements of the customer. The vast majority of studies that have been conducted on quality and supply chain management have concentrated their attention on the interaction that occurs between the inspection efforts of buyers and the quality provision efforts of suppliers. A number of authors (Lim, 2001; Reyniers & Tapiero, 1995; Tagaras & Lee, 1996) take into consideration a quality definition that is based on manufacturing. The perception of high quality is often associated with a heightened likelihood of a product or service being devoid of any defects. Various strategies are acknowledged to achieve superior quality in the manufacturing process. The principal focus of our inquiry pertains to quality factors that exert an impact on the level of demand emanating from consumers in the marketplace, including the degree of appropriateness for the intended function of the product. The present study examines a consumer demand function that exhibits a positive slope in response to an increase in quality level and a negative slope in response to a decrease in sales price. The authors (Tagaras & Lee, 1996) did not incorporate market demand functions into their analysis. The existing models did not consider the impact of partner interaction within the supply chain on the ultimate product quality and price and, consequently, the corresponding influence on customer demand and profitability.

The act of purchasing goods online is categorized as a non-store shopping experience, which presents a challenge for consumers in terms of evaluating the quality of physical products. This is due to the fact that consumers are limited to

relying solely on the information, sketches, visuals, graphics, and pictures presented on their computer screens. Consequently, the products that have been purchased may fail to perform as advertised. Quality risk pertains to the possibility that a procured item may not perform in accordance with its intended specifications (Ariff et al., 2014). The issue pertains to the risk of product performance, whereby customers may incur losses when a brand or product fails to meet their expectations owing to the challenge of accurately assessing product quality through online channels (Bhatnagar et al., 2000). Previous studies have demonstrated that the apprehension of product or performance risk, specifically the concern that a product may not operate or perform as anticipated, is on the rise in the realm of online commerce (Almousa, 2011). In summary, the primary apprehensions when purchasing products online are rooted in the inability to physically touch, feel, test, or try them prior to purchase. These concerns ultimately contribute to an increased perception of product risk (Saprikis et al., 2010). Consequently, the following hypothesis is proposed considering the supported hypothesis of (Boshaeer 2021):

H2: Quality risk has a negative impact on consumers' online shopping intention.

1.3.4 Perceived delivery risk and online shopping intention:

While infrequent, it is a common concern among online shoppers that they may not receive their ordered products (Ariff et al., 2014). When there is loss or damage to goods, customers are worried that their orders will not arrive on time. This pertains to the possibility of incurring delivery losses. The receipt of goods by the customer may be influenced by various factors, including but not limited to mishandling of items during the delivery process. It is imperative for customers to receive precise information regarding the shipment status in order to anticipate the arrival date of the product, which will help them think less about shipping and undeliverable products (Masoud, 2013). The incorrect person gets the products and is transferred to them in the wrong location, indicating that the delivery risk was a defect that might result in the products being lost, damaged, or assigned to the incorrect address after the order had been confirmed (Ariff et al., 2014). According to Naiyi (2004), customers are concerned about the shipping process because a product may be damaged during transportation, delivered to the incorrect address, or take longer than anticipated

in certain instances, worries about possible product damage throughout shipping, and the packaging of the product may not be suitable. Consequently, the possibility of non-delivery is one of the primary concerns of customers who intend to buy items online.

Alterations in technological infrastructure are now required of businesses in order for them to accomplish their many objectives. This change is being made in order to better keep up with the times, achieve a balance with our competitors, and pave the way for any previous plans or expectations (Koc, 2017). Each new advancement in technology brings with it some measure of convenience (Chesbrough, 2020). In recent days, companies have been concentrating their efforts on developing strategies to improve customer service for the delivery of orders by drone. Because of all the challenges that come along with using this method, it has been challenging for us to incorporate it into our regular routines up until this point. Also, businesses, particularly those in the technology sector, have recently begun to make significant headway in this area (Levy, 2017). As per a study that was carried out in the United States, irrespective of the findings of COVID-19, consumers appear to be in the process of accepting services that are provided by drone delivery. The findings of this study indicate that forty-seven percent of customers are enthusiastic about the prospect of drone delivery, and that 29% of those customers will make use of drone delivery within the next five years, 23% of those individuals will show interest in this technology given the current state of affairs as well. The delivery of packages using drones, which was initially considered to be the delivery system of the future (Lidynia et al., 2017), This new logistical infrastructure, which is being prepared to replace traditional delivery methods, may offer solutions to environmental and human health-related problems (K. Zhu, 2020).

A significant number of publications have expressed a particular interest in the problem of determining the optimum number of suppliers. In point of fact, hedging against the risk of supply disruption typically involves using dual or multiple sources of supply rather than a single source.

The study conducted by (Wai et al., 2019) investigates the impact of psychological and marketing variables on the purchasing behavior of consumers. It is suggested that the crucial elements for successful online shopping practices include customer support, devotion, and confidence in the procedures of the vendor (Masoud, 2013). According to (Wai et al., 2019), the inclusion of a well-defined policy

regarding returns has a significant impact on boosting the supplier's sales. A feasible return policy offers consumers the impetus, assurance, and ease of mind that the merchandise they have procured may be returned in the event that it fails to meet their requirements (Dailey & Ülkü, 2018). Notwithstanding the potential positive impact of a permissive return policy on stimulating online purchasing behavior, it is worth acknowledging that certain enterprises implement stringent return policies as a means of ensuring that buyers exhibit adequate deliberation when making a purchase decision (Oghazi et al., 2018). Drawing from the preceding discourse and considering relevant studies such as (Boshaer 2021; Wai T et al., 2019) the present investigation posits the following hypothesis:

H3: Delivery risk has a negative impact on consumers' online shopping intention.

CHAPTER 2: METHODOLOGY

2.1 Population and Sample:

Consumer shopping behavior is crucial to an organization's success, and it is affected by a wide variety of both internal and external factors (Svatosova, 2020). According to (Huseynov & Yıldırım, 2016), a good Internet marketing strategy is designed and implemented by taking into account the factors and motivations of online consumers. It has been proven by (Pilić et al., 2017) that the primary motivation of online shoppers is to find a lower price, followed by the convenience of shopping from home and the convenience of purchasing online. Older internet shoppers, on the other hand, care almost exclusively about ease of access. To meet the goal of this research and avoid biased data, this study focuses on the appropriate sample, namely, Turkish customers who have engaged in online shopping over the past three months.

In this research, convenience-based data is collected from online shoppers in Ankara, Türkiye, namely shoppers who make online purchases through local and foreign online platforms serving the Turkish market. The period of data collecting is from December 2022 to March 2023, and the data was collected online using a Google Form. In order to ease the collection of high-quality data, the questionnaire was translated into Turkish. This study aimed for a sample size of 300 participants because when the sample size (n) reaches 200 or more, it is advisable to consider that models are deemed statistically acceptable (Hoelster, 1983).

2.2 The Instrument for Data Collection

Structured questionnaires are used to collect the data. A questionnaire consisting of structured, concise questions was developed and administered to participants, who were instructed to select a response from a predetermined list of options. The survey instrument comprises a total of 22 questions, which are separated into two parts. The first part consists of screening questions and respondent demographics, and the second part consists of factors' assessment questions. The questionnaire was performed through Google Forms, which shared on social media platforms (e.g., Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp). For this study, the researcher employed a self-administered questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale to gather respondents' perceptions of risk factors influencing the intention of Turkish consumers to purchase online.

The questionnaire begins with a screening question regarding recent online shopping experience within the last three months, followed by questions regarding gender, age, marital status, education level, monthly income, and preferred shopping platform. In this study, the independent variable is the perceived risk, whereas intention to shop online is the dependent variable. 15 items were integrated into the research setting, containing questions for every variable, including PFR (Wai Tham et al., 2019) (4 items), PQR (Javadi et al., 2012; Nepomuceno et al., 2014) (3 items), PDR (Javadi et al., 2012) (4 items), and SI (Hsu et al., 2014) (4 items) as seen in **Table-1**. To construct a questionnaire, the researcher employed basic and unambiguous language, making it easy for each respondent to comprehend and answer the questions. In the process of statistical analysis, the researcher employed a technique of reversing the delivery risk factors in SPSS. This was done due to the positively worded nature of the items, because they represent positive expression in a negative situation (in our case, it is perceived risk) whereas the perceived delivery risk was coded to PDR, the reversed items coded as RPDR with the aim of mitigating the potential for response bias.

Table 1- Questionnaire items

Variable	Factor
Perceived Financial Risk	<p>PFR1- I check the reliability of the shopping platform.</p> <p>PFR2- I am concerned about my credit/debit card security.</p> <p>PFR3- I compare prices with other shopping platforms to get the most value for my money.</p> <p>PFR4- I might face common Online payment issues (Fraud, chargeback, system downtime, etc.)</p>
Perceived Quality Risk	<p>PQR1- might get faulty or low-quality products.</p> <p>PQR2- The product would offer the same degree of benefits I would anticipate.</p> <p>PQR3- It is difficult to evaluate the quality of products purchased online.</p>
Perceived Delivery Risk	<p>PDR1- I might have the delivery status updates.</p> <p>PDR2- The product will be delivered on time.</p> <p>PDR3- I prefer a reliable shipper to place an order.</p> <p>PDR4- I have the option to choose the shipping company.</p>
Shopping Intention	<p>SI1- I am currently considering a purchase from this platform.</p> <p>SI2- I would seriously consider purchasing from this platform.</p> <p>SI3- It is possible that I will make a purchase from this platform.</p> <p>SI4- I would recommend to friends and family the platform I use for online shopping.</p>

2.3 Plan for Data Analysis

The data is collected through a Google Forms survey and is automatically saved. It is then exported as a Microsoft Excel file and analyzed using SPSS.

The following analysis will be utilized in order to provide proofs that will support the research findings:

1. Reliability Analysis: Cronbach's alpha is a frequently utilized metric of reliability within the fields of social and organizational sciences (Bonett & Wright, 2015).
2. Correlation Analysis: is a statistical technique utilized to understand the magnitude and orientation of the linear association existing between two variables (Pallant, 2020).
3. Regression Analysis: is utilized to illustrate the linear relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variable (Tripepi et al., 2008).

2.4 Research Model

The conceptual framework is shown in *Figure 2*. This model was proposed after carefully reviewing the relevant studies. The elements with a significant impact are chosen for further examination. Online shopping intention is the dependent variable, the effect of these particular risk factors has to be reevaluated in this research. Thus, financial, quality, and delivery risks are used as independent variables.

Figure 2- Conceptual framework

CHAPTER 3: FINDINGS

3.1 Descriptive Analysis

The study was conducted online, and 300 individuals who had completed at least one transaction using an online purchasing platform within the most recent three months participated. The following tables contain information regarding the participants' demographics.

Table 2- Gender distribution

	Frequency	Percent
Female	194	64.7
Male	106	35.3
Total	300	100

There was a total of 194 female participants in the survey, representing 64.7% of the participants, and 106 male participants, representing 35.3% (See **Table 2**).

Table 3-Age

Age group	Frequency	Percent
18-25	29	9.7
26-35	172	57.3
36-45	99	33
Total	300	100

The majority of respondents are between the ages of 26 and 35, representing 57.3%, and 32.3% are between the ages of 36 and 45; 9.7% are between 18 and 25; the least percentage is for the respondents aged between 46 and 55, representing 0.7% of the sample. This can be viewed as the age group with the biggest proportion of working people with greater incomes and fewer obligations, thus motivating individuals to engage in increased online purchasing activities (See **Table 3**).

Table 4-Marital status

	Frequency	Percent
Single	88	29.3
Married	212	70.7
Total	300	100

As per the data presented in **Table 4**, a majority of 70.7% of the participants are reported to be married, while the remaining 29.3% are identified as single.

Table 5-Education level

Education level	Frequency	Percent
High school or equivalent	7	2.3
Bachelor's degree	199	66.3
Master's degree	89	29.7
Doctorate	5	1.7
Total	300	100

Table 5 indicates that the educational attainment of the participants is notably elevated. A significant majority of the participants, exceeding 97%, possess a bachelor's degree or a higher level of academic qualification. The educational attainment of the population under consideration is distributed as follows: 66.3% hold a bachelor's degree, 29.7% possess a master's degree, 1.7% have obtained a doctoral degree, and the remaining 2.3% have completed high school or an equivalent level of education.

Table 6-Monthly income

Income group	Frequency	Percent
TRY 6000 - TRY 8000	75	25
TRY 8001 - TRY 10000	167	55.7
More than TRY 10001	58	19.3
Total	300	100

Ankara regions had a mean annual equivalized household disposable income of 46,516 TL in 2021, whereas the average annual income of Türkiye was 37,400 TL (TUIK, 2021a). However, in order to take into consideration the working families' ability to maintain their standard of living, the minimum wage was raised in December of 2022 (TÜRK-İŞ, 2022). See above **Table 6** for participants' monthly income data.

Table 7-Preferred shopping platform

Platform	Frequency	Percent
Amazon	85	28.3
Hepsiburada	45	15
N11	137	45.7
Other	33	11
Total	300	100

According to **Table 7**, the respondents were distributed based on the preferred shopping platform used: 45.7% use n11, 28.3% prefer Amazon, 15% of the respondents are using Hepsiburada, 5.7% shop with Trendyol, 4.3% use Getir service, and 1% use other online shopping platforms.

3.2 Statistical Analysis

3.2.1 Reliability test

The research in question is deemed to possess a high degree of reliability due to its adherence to the criteria for good and excellent ratings, which necessitate a reliable alpha value exceeding 0.70 (Cronbach, 1951).

Table 8-Reliability test

Variable	No. of items	Cronbach's Alpha
PFR	4	.847
PQR	3	.855
PDR	4	.842
SI	4	.865

Table 8 presents a summary of the scales for all four variables, indicating that the reliability scores fall within the range of 0.842 to 0.865. The findings of the reliability test indicate that the score is satisfactory, adequate, and acceptable.

3.2.2 Correlations

The correlation analysis based on Pearson correlation is displayed in **Table 9**.

Table 9- Correlation analysis

Variable	PFR	RPDR	PQR	SI
PFR	1			
RPDR	.581**	1		
PQR	.685**	.671**	1	
SI	-.690**	-.694**	-.871**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The correlation between independent and dependent variables, which is illustrated in the above correlation table, for instance, a negative correlation was found between Perceived Financial risk with shopping intention ($r = -.690$, $p < 0.05$), while a negative correlation was also found between Perceived Delivery Risk and Shopping Intention ($r = -.694$, $p < 0.05$) and finally there was a negative correlation between Perceived Quality Risk and Shopping Intention ($r = -.871$, $p < 0.05$). In addition to the significance level of 0.000 for each variable, the relationship between the three variables and online shopping intention is also significant. The correlation coefficients of all variables fall within the range of -0.690 to -0.871. The signage displayed at the front signifies the positive or negative correlation (Pallant, 2020). Indicating that the association between the independent variable and the dependent variable is moderate to strong (Burgund et al., 2023), and that risk perception factors have a negative and statistically significant relationship with online shopping intention.

3.2.3 Regression analysis

The following tables depict the results of the multiple regression analysis. Specifically, **Table 10** presents the model summary. The table presents the adjusted R^2 and standard error of the estimate as metrics to assess the performance of a regression model.

Table 10-Regression

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Adjusted R Squared
Regression	1975.398	3	658.466	371.899	.000	.788
Residual	524.082	296	1.771			
Total	2499.480	299				

Dependent Variable: Shopping Intention

R^2 denotes the fraction of the variability in the response variable that can be elucidated by the predictor variables. To be precise, it represents the proportion of the variation that is attributable to the regression model, which surpasses the variation that can be accounted for by the model (Tabachnick et al., 2013). The coefficient denoted by 0.79 signifies that the independent variables under consideration account for 79% of the variance observed in the dependent variable.

The F-value presented in *Table 10* functions as an indicator of the regression model's fit with the data ($F(3, 296) = 371.899$) (Tabachnick et al., 2013).

Table 11-Coefficient

Model	Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
Perceived Financial Risks	-.137	-3.654	.000	.503	1.986
Perceived Delivery Risks	-.169	-4.598	.000	.522	1.915
Perceived Quality Risks	-.664	-16.128	.000	.418	2.391

The section of multiple regression analysis that pertains to collinearity diagnostics. This can reveal multicollinearity issues that may not be apparent from the correlation matrix. The findings are displayed in the table of coefficients. The second parameter of interest is the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). According to Pallant (2020), the presence of multicollinearity can be a matter of concern when VIF values exceed 10; In *Table 11* where VIF values are within the acceptable level (1.986, 1.915, and 2.391).

The effect of perceived financial risk on online buying behavior was found to be negative and significant ($\beta = -0.137$, $p < 0.05$), similarly, the effect of the risk factor for perceived delivery was negative and significant ($\beta = -.169$, $p < 0.05$), and lastly, the effect of quality perceived risk was negative and significant ($\beta = -.664$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, H1, H2, and H3 were supported.

3.2.4 t-tests

The Independent Sample t-test is used to investigate whether or not there are differences in shopping intention and risk factors based on gender and marital status (Pallant, 2020).

Table 12- t-test gender

	Gender	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	t value	p value
Shopping Intention	Female	194	13.88	2.855	.780	.436
	Male	106	13.60	2.962		
Perceived Financial Risk	Female	194	9.03	3.151	-1.042	.298
	Male	106	9.43	3.298		
Perceived Quality Risk	Female	194	6.79	2.760	-1.565	.119
	Male	106	7.33	2.975		
Perceived Delivery Risk	Female	194	9.39	3.286	-.729	.467
	Male	106	9.68	3.396		

Table 12 presented the t-test results. Risk perceptions of participants' shopping intention did not differ according to gender. In other words, these values were found to be similar.

Table 13- t-test marital status

	Gender	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	t value	p value
Shopping Intention	Single	88	13.40	3.250	-1.478	.140
	Married	212	13.94	2.721		
Perceived Financial Risk	Single	88	9.31	3.378	.464	.643
	Married	212	9.12	3.135		
Perceived Quality Risk	Single	88	7.24	3.155	1.002	.317
	Married	212	6.88	2.706		
Perceived Delivery Risk	Single	88	9.80	3.481	1.026	.306
	Married	212	9.36	3.255		

In the same sense, regarding marital status, in **Table 13**, a significant effect of marital status on the variables was not found ($p > 0.05$).

3.2.5 ANOVA test

The utilization of One-way ANOVA can determine the presence of statistically significant variations in the average scores of the variables among the groups (Pallant, 2020).

Table 14-Age groups towards shopping intention

Age group	n	Mean	F	p value	Post-hoc
a. 18-25	29	15.24	3.216	.023	a>b, a>c
b. 26-35	172	13.74			
c. Over 36	99	13.56			
Total	300	13.75			

Shopping intention was examined across age groups and results demonstrate that homogeneity of variance was not violated ($p=0.064 > 0.05$). The shopping intentions of people of varying ages are outlined in **Table 14**, ($F=3.216$, $p=.023$), showing a significant difference between age groups towards shopping intention. In order to find the difference between groups, it is crucial to examine post-hoc mean differences. It was found that participants younger than 25 have significant differences over older age groups.

Table 15-Age groups towards perceived financial risks

Age group	n	Mean	F	p value	Post-hoc
a. 18-25	29	7.72	3.633	.013	c > a
b. 26-35	172	9.07			
c. Over 36	99	9.78			
Total	300	9.17			

Table 15 shows the comparison of perceived financial risk among age groups. When Homogeneity of variance was examined, it was seen that it was not violated ($p = 0.929 > 0.05$). ANOVA results were showed that there was a significant difference between age groups ($F = 3.633$, $p=.013$). It is essential to examine the mean differences for post-hoc. Accordingly, it can be said that mean value of participants who are older than 36 is significantly higher than the participants who ranged between 18-25.

Table 16- Age groups towards delivery risks

Age group	n	Mean	F	p value
18-25	29	8.72	1.217	.304
26-35	172	9.41		
Over 36	99	9.85		
Total	300	9.49		

The same comparison can be continued for perceived delivery risks; homogeneity of variance was not violated (sig. value =0.200 > 0.05). All age groups had similar attitudes toward delivery risks; no significant influence was found in **Table 16**, (F = 1.217, p =.304 > 0.05).

Table 17-Age groups towards quality risks

Age group	N	Mean	F	p value	Post-hoc
a. 18-25	29	5.62	3.461	.017	c > a
b. 26-35	172	6.94			
c. Over 36	99	7.46			
Total	300	6.98			

Consequently, **Table 17** represents differences of age groups to the perceived quality risks. It was observed that homogeneity of variance was not violated (sig. value =0.091 > 0.05) and that there was a significant effect among age groups to the perceived quality risks (F =3.461, p value =.017). Therefore, it is required to test post-hoc mean differences to reveal the different group. Hence, it is noticeable that participants over the age of 36 have a significant difference over the youngest age group when encountering quality risks.

Table 18-Monthly income towards shopping intention

Monthly income	n	Mean	F	p value
TRY 6000 – TRY 8000	75	14.25	.202	.895
TRY 8001 – TRY 10000	167	13.74		
More than TRY 10001	58	13.72		
Total	300	13.78		

In a similar manner for age groups, the same analysis for the monthly income can be carried out, and the findings are presented in upcoming tables. The homogeneity of variance was not violated ($p = 0.929 > 0.05$) so that it can be continued to ANOVA test interpretation, by examining the data in *Table 18*, it is clear that there was no significant difference in the mean scores on the shopping intention in terms of monthly income ($F = .202, p > 0.05$).

Table 19- Monthly income towards perceived financial risks

Monthly income	n	Mean	F	p value
TRY 6000 - TRY 8000	75	8.59	.489	.690
TRY 8001 - TRY 10000	167	9.34		
More than TRY 10001	58	9.14		
Total	300	9.17		

Table 19 represents the differences between monthly income groups regarding the perceived financial risks. Homogeneity of variance was not violated ($p = 0.993 > 0.05$); it seems that age groups do not have a significant difference towards financial risks ($F = .489, p > 0.05$).

Table 20- Monthly income towards perceived delivery risks

Monthly income	n	Mean	F	p value
TRY 6000 - TRY 8000	75	9.46	.015	.998
TRY 8001 - TRY 10000	167	9.49		
More than TRY 10001	58	9.55		
Total	300	9.49		

The differences between monthly income groups regarding the perceived delivery risks. Homogeneity of variance was not violated ($p = 0.984 > 0.05$). As seen in *Table 20*, all age groups show no significant difference towards delivery risks ($F = .015, p > 0.05$).

Table 21- Monthly income towards quality risks

Monthly income	n	Mean	F	p value
TRY 6000 - TRY 8000	16	6.95	.642	.589
TRY 8001 - TRY 10000	167	7.13		
More than TRY 10001	58	7.00		
Total	300	6.98		

Lastly, **Table 21** represents differences of monthly income groups to the perceived quality risks, homogeneity of variance was not violated ($p = 0.870 > 0.05$) it was observed that there was no significant effect of age groups to the perceived quality risks ($F = .642, p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

Conclusion

As a result of this research, it can be said that there is a negative relationship between perceived risks and online shopping intention, encountering higher risks will lead to less shopping. Furthermore, it has been observed that variables such as gender and monthly income do not significantly influence individuals' shopping intentions as well as the perceived risks. Whereas age has a significant difference in terms of shopping intention, financial risk, and quality risk but no significance towards delivery risk. Pi & Sangruang, (2011) study found that the perception of risk significantly impacts negative attitudes towards online shopping. The study employed a total of seven distinct risk factors, namely convenience, financial, physical, psychological, implementation, social, and time. The primary conjecture posits that individuals' overall perception of risk is inversely related to their attitudes towards online shopping. The convenience, financial, physical, performance, and social factors are the primary determinants of customer attitude, with perception risk being the most influential factor. The findings of their study indicate that the five risks associated with online shopping that were examined hold significant importance.

In this regard, several researchers found that the attitude of consumers towards online shopping is negatively impacted by quality risk, financial risk, and delivery risk. Which was in line with the findings of this study (Ariff et al., 2014; Masoud, 2013; Wai Tham et al., 2019). The results of this study also corroborate the findings of Bhatnagar et al., (2000), because they found that consumers would be less likely to make an online purchase if they were aware of the potential risk associated with the item they were considering to buy.

Hence, it can be said that the findings of this research are in line with the literature's findings. Comprehending the significance and function of diverse facets of perceived risk is of utmost importance for electronic retailers. Consequently, they can implement risk mitigation tactics that are tailored to the specific type of risk involved.

Theoretical implication

The most significant outcome that this study has contributed is a model that describes the impact of different kinds of perceived risks on online shopping. The findings of this research are applicable to customers in Türkiye; nevertheless, the survey that was utilized for the analysis is adaptable for usage in any nation. The effect of perceived risk on online shopping can provide consumers and businesses with useful information in a variety of different ways if it is investigated. When it comes to customers, if they are aware of the many sorts of perceived risks that have an impact on online purchasing, then they may believe that these types of risks ought to be taken into consideration when engaging in online shopping. Consequently, consumers had to give a greater amount of thought to the many forms of effectively perceived risks whenever they make purchases online. For the companies, each and every form of risk is significant, and while they should take enough safeguards, they should take further actions to lower the perception of risk when it comes to the more effective risks. Customers' perceptions of high risk will lead to a reduction in their level of online shopping. If companies do not take appropriate and timely action, they run the risk of incurring significant losses.

One of the most significant conclusions from this research is that customers are less likely to buy online when they are shopping on an unfamiliar platform or when they have less information about the platform they intend to purchase from. On the other hand, when there is high creditability for a well-known shopping platform, customers are less likely to experience hesitation and are more likely to complete the transaction.

Practical implications

Comprehending the significance and function of diverse facets of perceived risk is of utmost importance for electronic retailers. Consequently, they can implement risk mitigation tactics that are tailored to the specific type of risk in the matter.

It is recommended to instruct and motivate clients to utilize the payment guarantee method and enhance security by utilizing an intermediary payment system such as an electronic wallet. Those techniques are designed to protect the buyer in the form of payments on hold and trust-mark certification on prestige sales websites.

Moreover, shoppers must be informed that they will incur no fees while utilizing this secure payment method.

Enterprises should build a website security mechanism that ensures customer funds in order to create peace of mind for customers when dealing with business platforms. The size of this risk is usually considered as one of the main concerns of online shoppers, although the payment system has been developed and has received customer acceptance of online shopping.

In order to enhance customer engagement and attract attention towards the website, it is imperative for the provider to implement a stringent quality control process for product diversification. To be successful, businesses supplying products or services must prioritize product branding, provide a high-quality guarantee, and provide great after-sales care straight from the manufacturer. The expansion of enterprise product development can significantly impact the online shopping experience for customers. However, the inability to regulate product quality may lead to an increase in perceived risk among consumers. In the realm of online commerce, it is imperative for businesses to take into account the quality assurance measures associated with the authentication source, origin, warranty, and product brand, particularly in the case of products geared towards men, such as technology products and electronics.

In the realm of online shopping, it is required for business advertisements to maintain a level of honesty to establish a sense of trust and confidence among potential customers. It is imperative that customers are furnished with comprehensive information regarding the quality of products featured on the website, encompassing details such as color, size, material, style, warranty, and specifications. In addition, it is essential that this data is complemented by product visuals. Vendors are advised to incorporate both 3-D renderings and authentic depictions of the product to provide customers with a more comprehensive understanding of the items they are purchasing. This approach may serve to mitigate the perceived risk associated with the transaction and bolsters the customer's purchasing intent.

The concerns of consumers pertained to the delivery of their orders, as they apprehended the possibility of product damage during handling and transportation or the receipt of a defective or non-compliant item. To ensure prompt and secure delivery

of merchandise, it is advisable for online retailers to engage with reputable and reliable shipping service providers. This measure can help mitigate the risk of potential delays or damages that may occur during the transportation of goods. It is advisable for online retailers to mitigate the risk of return policies by establishing unambiguous policies and procedures and strictly complying with the policy guidelines.

The proliferation of the Internet has resulted in a shift in the shopping behavior of consumers. There is a growing trend among consumers to shift towards the practice of online shopping. The disparity between internet users and online shoppers is substantial, primarily due to concerns regarding online risks. However, this situation presents novel prospects for e-retailers. It is imperative to comprehend the notion of perceived risk and consistently monitor it, given its correlation with the human element. This research adds to the existing literature on the evolution of consumers' risk perception in response to various factors in recent times.

Research limitation

Due to the fact that data collection took place at a limited number of geographical location in Türkiye, the study does have some restrictions when it comes to the representation of the sample and the composition of the sample. In addition, the research did not take into account online shopping in specific contexts, such as clothing, electronic devices or the other goods. The questionnaire being carried out is constructed online, and respondents received a link to it. Participants may have made some errors while answering the survey. Inadvertently selecting the incorrect answer may lead to potential biased answers (Özsurunc, 2017).

The research centered on three aspects of perceived risk. Subsequent researchers may replicate this investigation by considering a comprehensive construct of perceived risk or investigate different aspects of perceived risk.

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APPENDIX 1: QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondents

I am currently preparing MBA program; my topic is The Effect Of Perceived Risks On Online Shopping Intention: A Case Of Ankara.

I appreciate it if you spare some time and effort to complete this survey questionnaire; the information will only be used for academic purposes.

Your participation in this survey is highly appreciated; if you have any inquiry, please do not hesitate to contact me:

Alaa Taban Al Hlaichi

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Graduate Dept. Of Management

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1. I have shopped online in the past three months
 Yes No
2. Gender
 Male Female
3. Age
 18-25 26-35 Over 36
4. Marital status
 Single Married
5. Education level
 Less than high school High school or equivalent
 Bachelor's degree Master's degree Doctorate
6. Personal Monthly Income
 TRY6000 -TRY 8000 TRY 8001 -TRY10000 More than TRY 10001
7. Preferred Online Shopping Platform

- Amazon Hepsiburada Trendyol
 N11
 Getir Other

Please consider the online platform you have chosen when answering the questions below.

STATEMENT	SCALE				
	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
I check the reliability of the shopping platform.					
I am concerned about my credit/debit card security.					
I compare prices with other shopping platforms to get the most value for my money.					
I might face common Online payment issues (Fraud, chargeback, system downtime, etc.)					
I might get faulty or low-quality products.					
The product would offer the same degree of benefits I would anticipate.					
It is difficult to evaluate the quality of products purchased online.					
I might have the delivery status updates.					
The product will be delivered on time.					

I prefer a reliable shipper to place an order.					
I have the option to choose the shipping company.					
I am currently considering a purchase from this platform.					
I would seriously consider purchasing from this platform.					
It is possible that I will make a purchase from this platform.					
I would recommend to friends and family the platform I use for online shopping.					

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PetroChina International Halfaya	Sr. Specialist	2011

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Publications:

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